

DATA MANAGEMENT AND CREATION OF ROUTES FOR AUTOMATED VEHICLES IN SMART CITY

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ABSTRACT

Automated and Autonomous vehicle has attracted considered interest in recent decade by leveraging the current telecommunication networks in order to reduce the traffic in both air and road network and to reduce the cost of fuel cost communication and reduce emissions and finally mitigates the parking related issues in the smart cities. However current telecommunication networks suffer from simultaneously handling the heterogeneous vehicle data traffic and network component failure due to natural disaster. In order to manage those challenges, a new distributed failure tolerant path planning framework has been modelled to generate the virtual path for automated

vehicles like drone and grounded vehicles. Due to advent of artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies in the software defined networks, efficient management of the automated vehicle is feasible using existing telecommunication network like 3G/4G and LTE networks. Proposed model integrates architecture with the Amazon or IBM webservice to gather and manage the network data and its communications. Web Server has been deployed with developed virtual path planning algorithm to control the autonomous vehicles on extracting the various information from the sensor component in the ecosystem using telecommunication network. Base station also categorizes and schedules the data efficiently to reduce the computation time and cost. Especially each node which is considered as sensor or transceiver is capable of operating in fixed speed for specific data size and it is configured in transformers in electric grids, street lights, and overhead electric lines in railways and medians in the road. In order to increase the limit, data compression and signal amplification is enabled through amplifier connected with sensor or transceiver component. Further optical fibre channel is employed for data communication between transceiver and base station in the web server whereas two transceivers can be connected in wireless manner to reduce the dependence of the optical fibre. Controlled signal is transferred to transceiver built-in in the autonomous devices through trajectory of the intermediate transceivers. Control signal carries the information of the virtual path plan as route map containing the route number of the optical fiber channel and specific identification number of transceiver representing start and end point destinations for movement. Finally transceiver communicates the information like speed limit, signal indication like one way and closed roads etc. Experimental analysis of the proposed model is evaluated on various aspects. In that proposed architecture capable of controlling various devices in high heterogeneous traffics without loss of control signal. Proposed framework can be transformed to concept of intelligent transportation system for eco friendly smart cities.

Keywords: Autonomous Vehicles, Smart Cities, Virtual Path, Path Planning Approach, Signal Controlling, Signal transmission, Data Communication, Intelligent Transportation system.

Cite this Article: Mukesh, V., Joel, D., Balaji, V. M., Tamilpriyan, R., & Yogesh Pandian, S. (2024). Data management and creation of routes for automated vehicles in smart city. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(36), 2119–2150.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_182.pdf

I. Introduction

Due to urbanization, purpose of the smart city for economic development of country and improvement of quality of life of peoples is enabling the vital importance. Ecosystem of smart city has to be improved on utilization of technologies. Especially ecosystem is polluted by the emission of vehicles. Hence various advancement of the technologies has been deployed to manage the challenges of the ecosystem. Especially incorporation of sensor along the current telecommunication network manages the resource and services of the city effectively. Despite of various advantageous of current telecommunication architecture such as 5G and LTE networks, it fails manage the heterogeneous traffic and failure of the network component due to physical or environment disasters.

In order to tackle those challenges, a new distributed failure tolerant path planning framework has been modelled to generate the virtual path for automated vehicles like drone and grounded vehicles. Due to advent of artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies in the software defined networks, efficient management of the automated vehicle is feasible using existing telecommunication network like 3G/4G and LTE networks. Proposed model integrates architecture with the Amazon or IBM webserver to gather and manage the network data and its communications. Web Server has been deployed with developed virtual path planning algorithm to control the autonomous vehicles on extracting the various information from the sensor component in the ecosystem using telecommunication network.

Base station also categories and schedules the data efficiently to reduce the computation time and cost. Especially each node which considered as sensor or transceiver is capable of the operating in fixed speed for specific data size and it is configured in transformers in electric grids, street lights, and overhead electric lines in railways and medians in the road. In order to increase the limit, data compression and signal amplification is enabled through amplifier connected with sensor or transceiver component. Further optical fibre channel is employed for data communication between transceiver and base station in the web server whereas two transceivers can be connected in wireless manner to reduce the dependence of the optical fibre.

Controlled signal is transferred to transceiver built-in in the autonomous devices through trajectory of the intermediate transceivers. Control signal carries the information of the virtual path plan as route map containing the route number of the optical fiber channel and specific identification number of transceiver representing start and end point destinations for movement. Finally transceiver communicates the information like speed limit, signal indication like one ways and closed roads etc. Experimental analysis of the proposed model is evaluated on various aspects. In that proposed architecture capable of controlling various devices in high heterogeneous traffics without loss of control signal.

1.2 OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT

- To manage and control data in smart cities at the same time giving access to data to all the devices present in the ecosystem.
- Creating a virtual pathway for automated vehicles and drones in a smart city and at a national level.
- Creating a neural link for all the devices, vehicles and gadgets in the Smart cities.
- The system is developed and implemented by reducing the impact on the environment of existing systems.

1.2 SMART CITIES

Smart cities are normal cities which integrate IoT, Wot and Cot devices along with automated vehicles and devices, smart gadgets and sensors working together for the wellness of the people in the cities. Smart cities are cities of the future where everything is automated and controlled by AI and machines without the intervention of humans for the welfare of the humans. Smart cities are only developed by synchronised working of all the elements and devices present in the ecosystem or smart cities at the same time the ability of the devices to function independently is also required for smart cities to function. With the help of the main framework the smart cities can respond and react to the changes in the environment, in simple terms a smart city is one huge complex setup of urban area by combining many small networks of smart and automated devices

Fig 1.1: Representation of smart cities

1.2.1 WORKING

A Smart City has its main driver in the use of innovation and technological potential as tools for transformation and improvement of quality of life. Getting into the operational field, the implementation of sensors and IoT devices is used for collecting data from buildings, facilities, traffic systems, security, supplies, etc. To be processed and sent to specific management platforms, where they can be visualised, analysed and even operate in real time in different areas of the city.

Fig 1.2 Architecture of smart cities

1.3 AUTOMATED DEVICES AND VECHILES

The automated devices are devices which are capable of performing a task without any intervention of humans using either inbuilt sensors and technologies or by using external

sensors and technologies. AI and machine learning are used in these devices to function and perform the designated task. Automated Vehicle are an example of the automated devices which has ability to carry people or goods between places.

Automated Vehicle is one that can drive itself from a starting point to a destination in designated auto pilot mode using various in vehicle and navigation technologies without any intervention of humans to the process, the user decides the destination and the rest is taken care by the automated vehicle.

Fig 1,3 Working of automated vehicles using sensors

1.4EFFECTS ON HUMAN LIFE

When a smart cities ecosystem is achieved all the day to day task can be carried out by robots and machines that are pre designated to complete the task automated. Rather than working about the day to day world humans can be peace connected with people and appreciating the life given to them. The AI monitors every person in the city for their wellbeing and acts as a personal assistant to human. Human would blend with the machine and robots or human may become humanoids which makes the human half machine and half human. We as whole civilization will evolve to higher intelligent civilization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Based on the literature review as we observed that most of the health platforms used on real time-based detection which helps to detect various cancer problems. Most of the papers state that this Oral Cancer detection method is essential in this environment.

2.2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Mr S. Pallam Shetty: “An efficient machine learning optimization model for route establishment mechanism in IoT environment” IEEE access of journal section on computer networks and communication. Developing an optimization-based machine learning algorithm for route establishment in an IoT environment. The developed algorithm involved in the construction of whale optimization algorithm for classification of optimal path those estimated through optimization of the path in the network. The constructed network performance is evaluated based on the consideration of the optimal path in the network. The performance characteristics of the proposed WOABC are computed based on the evaluation of the routing path in the network. Simulation analysis stated that the proposed WOABC is comparatively examined based on the estimation of network parameters.

Mohammad Pasha: “Scalable and energy efficient task offloading schemes for vehicular cloud computing” Smart vehicles of today on road are equipped with advanced computational units, multiple communication technologies, intelligent sensing platforms, and human-computer interaction devices which utilize Vehicular Edge Networks to support services offered by the remote cloud. By using APEATOVC, I conveyed and versatile protocol for economical, efficient and effective task offloading in these networks which address the adaptability of vehicular clouds. The results obtained by extensive simulations are presented to assess and contrast its performance with existing protocols.

Leigh Duggan: “A Rapid Deployment Big Data Computing Platform for Cloud Robotics”. The production of a general cloud robotics architecture that leverages the established and evolving big data technologies. By providing a general-purpose architecture, it is hoped that this framework will allow future research to build upon and begin to create a standardized platform, where research can be easily repeated. Validated and compared. The secondary contribution is the critical evaluation of the design of cloud robotic architectures Whilst prior research has demonstrated that cloud-based robotic processing is achievable via big data technologies.

Sumedha Chauhan: “Addressing Big Data Challenges in Smart Cities: A Systematic Literature Review”. Its articulated that approximately 2.5 quintillion bytes of data is generated every day and 90% of the data in the world has been created in last two years alone. If this large volume of data, also called big data, is managed and analysed properly, it can create a major real impact on the functioning of smart cities Therefore, the valuable information drawn from big data analytics is quickly transforming cities into the artificial ecosystem of interdependent, interconnected and intelligent digital organisms. Given that big data provides the opportunities to resolve the issues arising in smart cities, it is important to address the challenges related to it.

EXISTING METHOD

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we see about existing models and framework for data management for IoT and smart devices. We also see about the existing models and framework for navigation for automated vehicles and drones.

3.2 DATA MANAGEMENT

The major and most predominant way of managing data is cloud computing where a data is stored in data centers around the world, these data are assessable by an internet connection so the data can be assessed at any time until having a reliable internet connection. The main drawback of the system is the user must pay the vendor for using and storing the data in data centers. Cloud computing is not as efficient as it was promised to be in the starting and it's not as developed to the level that it could be integrated in smart cities.

3.3 CLOUD COMPUTING

Cloud computing is an abstraction of compute, storage, and network infrastructure assembled as a platform on which applications and systems can be deployed quickly and scaled on the fly. Crucial to cloud computing is self-service: Users can simply fill in a web form and get up and running.

The vast majority of cloud customers consume public cloud computing services over the internet, which are hosted in large, remote data centers maintained by cloud providers. The most common type of cloud computing, SaaS (software as service), delivers prebuilt applications to the browsers of customers who pay per seat or by usage, exemplified by such popular apps as Salesforce, Google Docs, or Microsoft Teams. Next in line is IaaS (infrastructure as a service), which offers vast, virtualized compute, storage, and network

infrastructure upon which customers build their own applications, often with the aid of providers' API-accessible services.

Fig 3.1 Block diagram of cloud services

3.3.1 WORKING

There are 3 types of cloud computing development models and each one them is designed for a specific purpose and need.

3.3.1.1 PRIVATE CLOUD

Private cloud provides a proprietary cloud environment dedicated to a single business entity, with physical components stored on-premises or at a vendor's data center. Because the private cloud is only accessible to a single business, this model offers a high degree of control. Advantages include customized architecture, advanced security protocols, and the ability to extend computing resources in a virtualized environment as needed. In many cases, an organization maintains a private cloud infrastructure on-site while delivering cloud computing services to internal users via the intranet. In other instances, the organization contracts with a third-party cloud vendor to host and maintain exclusive servers off site.

3.3.1.2 PUBLIC CLOUD

Public cloud uses the internet to store and manage access to data and applications. It's completely virtualized, providing an environment where shared resources are leveraged as needed. Because these resources are delivered over the web, the public cloud deployment model allows organizations to scale more easily—the ability to pay for cloud resources as needed is a

huge advantage over local servers. In addition, public cloud service providers offer robust security measures to protect user data from being accessed by other tenants.

3.3.1.3 HYBRID CLOUD

Hybrid cloud combines private and public cloud models, allowing organizations to leverage the benefits of shared resources while using existing IT infrastructure for critical security requirements. The hybrid cloud model allows companies to store confidential data internally and access it via applications running in the public cloud. To comply with privacy regulations, for example, an organization could store sensitive user data in a private cloud and perform resource-intensive computation in the public cloud.

Fig 3.2 Architecture of cloud

3.5 NAVIGATION

The industry standard in Satellite navigation is the GPS (Global Positioning System) which is used in all the cars and in mobile phones to identify, locate and navigate around the world. GPS is a well and advanced navigation system for human use, it requires humans to interpret and respond to the recent changes in the specific geographical area and for real time changes in the environment this is why the GPS is not suitable for integrating in automated vehicles. Integrating GPS to drones may coz numerous accidents involving Drones as it may crash into the buildings or having aid air collation with other Drones.

3.6 GPS

GPS stands for Global Positioning System, originally Navistar GPS, and provides location, velocity and time synchronization based on a global satellite system. GPS is everywhere and has become a daily usage in most of the modern applications, such as smartphones and smartwatches. It is a crucial technology that shapes the future and assists many organizations all around the world to function. Some businesses are more depended on GPS than others.

The function of GPS is a satellite-based navigation system that tells you where you are on Earth, and the GPS provides people with current positioning, navigation, and time services. The purpose of GPS is to navigate us through one place to another. Global Positioning System is a free service that is owned and operated by the U.S. government.

3.6.1 WORKING

GPS works through a technique called trilateration. Used to calculate location, velocity and elevation, trilateration collects signals from satellites to output location information. It is often mistaken for triangulation, which is used to measure angles, not distances. Satellites orbiting the earth send signals to be read and interpreted by a GPS device, situated on or near the earth's surface. To calculate location, a GPS device must be able to read the signal from at least four satellites. Each satellite in the network circles the earth twice a day, and each satellite sends a unique signal, orbital parameters and time. At any given moment, a GPS device can read the signals from six or more satellites.

A single satellite broadcasts a microwave signal which is picked up by a GPS device and used to calculate the distance from the GPS device to the satellite. Since a GPS device only gives information about the distance from a satellite, a single satellite cannot provide much location information. Satellites do not give off information about angles, so the location of a GPS device could be anywhere on a sphere's surface area. Then a satellite sends a signal, it creates a circle with a radius measured from the GPS device to the satellite.

When we add a second satellite, it creates a second circle, and the location is narrowed down to one of two points where the circles intersect. With a third satellite, the device's location can finally be determined, as the device is at the intersection of all three circles. We live in a three-dimensional world, which means that each satellite produces a sphere, not a circle. The intersection of three spheres produces two points of intersection, so the point nearest Earth is chosen. As a device moves, the radius (distance to the satellite) changes. When the radius changes, new spheres are produced, giving us a new position. We can use that data, combined with the time from the satellite, to determine velocity, calculate the distance to our destination and the ETA.

Fig 3.3 Working of GPS tracking

WORKING METHODOLOGY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we see about proposed methodology and its benefits. Every project is unique and has its own operating environment and sets of technical requirements. As a result, the execution of a project is subject to numerous constraints that limit the commencement or progression of field operations, which invariably have significant negative impact on overall project performance. By definition, constraints refer to any condition, such as temporal/spatial limitations and safety/quality concerns, which may prevent a project to achieve its goals. Successful execution and control of a construction project relies on effective identification and management of constraints through master planning and short-term look-ahead scheduling.

4.2 PROPOSED METHOD

In this part, design and implementation of the framework on incorporation of data and control unit in the web server to control the transmission of the autonomous vehicles which acts as transceiver against the various fault occurring due to natural disaster has been modelled.

Further path planning for virtual path is been modelled utilizing artificial intelligence in the data and control unit. Proposed architecture of the particular framework is as follows

4.2.1 NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE

In network architecture, Autonomous vehicles incorporating the transceiver as destinations, transceiver incorporated in transformer in electric lines, overhead electrical lines in railway and in street light and median in the highways as intermediate hops, optical fibre channels for signal communication between transceiver and data and control unit in web server. Web server acts as base station. Details of the infrastructure has been illustrated as follows

4.2.2 AUTONOMOUS VEHICLE DEPLOYMENT

In this work, Autonomous vehicles incorporated with transceiver in the smart city is represented as $AV = \{v1, v2, \dots, vn\}$. It composed of heterogeneous vehicles with varied distance in the network are distributed dynamically over a specified region These autonomous vehicles embedded full duplex transceiver with transmitter and receiver elements, each of which constitutes the various control signals composed of speed limit, signal indications along the route map containing the route number representing the optical fibre and specific identification number of intermediate transmitter representing the virtual path[10].

4.2.3 TRANSCEIVER – INTERMEDIATE HOP

Transceiver which acts as intermediate hop or sink is composed of fixed unit represented in the transformer in electric grid, streetlights and median in highways and overhead electric lines in railways. These units are gathering the information of the autonomous vehicle and transmit the data and control unit for effective path planning. Transceiver in fixed unit is depicted a

Figure 4.1: Block Diagram of the proposed framework

The transceiver is powered by electric lines and its purpose to gather the information of the Autonomous vehicle either using optical fibre channel or it is capable connecting directly to another transformer if the distance between the transceiver is low[11]. Figure 4.1 represents the architecture of the proposed model. Transceiver acts as communication link between the data control unit and devices in the ecosystem.

4.2.4 DATA COLLECTION AND CONTROL UNIT

Web server like Amazon or IBM Oracle or Window Azure will be employed as base station to gather and manage the data of the transceiver and autonomous vehicles and its surrounding. Base station includes analysis and computing part to manage the collect data. Especially storage unit is to store the information on basis of various categories with location tags. In addition, it includes the processing unit to compute the dynamics of the vehicle information. Finally, it utilizes the Virtual path routing algorithm to generate the control signal to autonomous vehicle transportation

Path planning and routing algorithm uses the decision-making process employing the artificial intelligence and deep learning technique. Let $TC = \{Tc1, Tc2, \dots, Tcm\}$ represents the identified transceiver. The dynamic information of the vehicle is provided to the control unit through transceiver. Let Predicted Path is represented as $VP = (Vp0, Vp1, \dots, Vpm, Vp0)$ path which propagates as control signal to transceiver through optical fiber and reaches the destination autonomous vehicle $Av0$. The control signal will be transmitted from vehicle hop by hop propagation to provide decision to the vehicle [12].

4.2.5 DATA COMMUNICATION THROUGH SIGNAL SLICING

Signal transmitted by the transceiver uses the 5G telecommunication network, 5 G network is capable of slicing the signal into 11 channels. In this, first two channels permanently designated for connection between the transceivers. Next three channels which act as relay signal are used to transmit signal to the devices in the ecosystem. Further three channels in sequence are responsible for providing data connection and enabling the creation of virtual pathway for automated vehicles and drones by accommodating it. Accommodating of moving vehicle is achieved with the speed limit of 10kmph. Finally 3 channels of the sequence is considered as important and it facilities the communication between the devices in the ecosystem on enabling the devices to communicate between one and another by updating the real time changes in the environment.

Last 3 channels is capable of handling the communication of the device during fault or accident from the information from the neighbor devices. Transceivers are fitted with an amplifier which amplifies the strength of the signal. The data utilization frequency is different from the relayed data frequency by which the relaying device cannot access the relayed signal it can only access the signals it's authorized.

4.3.6 FAULT TOLERANCE MECHANISM

Every transceiver in the framework can connect up to an average of 40 devices in which one third is reserved for the devices that move slower than 10 km/h or be stationary in a place. The rest of one third is divided into two halves the first half is used to connect between the Transceiver and other half is reserved in case of an overload or in case of a disaster. The reserved half is kept in off until it needed it is kept in a way to escape attacks from EMP system or solar storms.

4.3 WORKING METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is mostly software driven than hardware driven the hardware is only a tool to communicate and transfer data within the main framework and the device in the ecosystem. It's all the processing power and analytical skills of the software that runs and controls the entire system. The software determines the nature and limits of any transceiver in the system. As the transceivers act as the connection link between the framework and the devices in the ecosystem.

The signal transmitted by the Transceiver in framework is goes under slicing which one could observe in 5G technology. In which the signal is sliced into 11 different channels in which 2 channels are permanently designated for connection between the transceivers in the framework. Another 3 channel are used to transmit signal to the devices in the ecosystem and which is also act as the relayed signal.

The next set of 3 channel are used to accommodate the automated vehicles and drones. These channels are responsible for providing data connection and enabling the creation of virtual pathway for automated vehicles and drones. This set of 3 channels are used to accommodate any moving devices above the speed limit of 10kmph. The last pair of 3 channels are the most important and make this system every special these last pair of 3 channels facilities the communication between the devices in the ecosystem which is independent of the data control and management centre as these last pair of 3 channels enable the devices to communicate between one and another to be updated in real time in the changes in the environment. In case of an accident all the devices in the area can act in reflex using the last 3 dedicated channels. Now coming into the user end devices every device is fixed with a

Transceiver on top of receiver and transmitter if present and these Transceivers are fitted with an amplifier which amplifies the strength of the signal. The data utilisation frequency is different from the relayed data frequency by which the relaying device cannot access the relayed signal it can only access the signals it's authorised. So, every device in the smart city ecosystem is connected to at least 2 Transceivers at any given time by the shortest possible route or by a minimal of strangers in-between. The data sent to the device takes the shortest route in the two options which is decided and analysed by the analytics section in the data control and management centre.

Every transceiver in the framework can connect up to an average of 40 devices in which one third is reserved for the devices that move slower than 10 km/h or be stationary in a place. The other one third is reserved for objects moving above the speed of above 10 km/h. The rest of one third is divided into two halves the first half is used to connect between the Transceiver in the framework and the other half is reserved in case of an overload or in case of a disaster. The reserved half is kept in off until it needed it is kept in a way to escape attacks from EMP system or solar storms. It's seen with complete caution that not any motion device is considered as a relay device for a stationary device.

Every optical fibre line is designated with a route number and every transceiver in an optical fibre line is given with a specific identify associated with the route number. Using this information, the virtual pathway is built upon this Routing Algorithm. This acts as a map for automated vehicles as every Transceiver is programmable by software the signals, signs and speed limits could be integrated within them. As devices are interconnected any real time change in the environment can be added to the system to avoid disasters.

The data control and management centre use a Euclid vector-based motion sensing software to understand the direction and speed of any object in the ecosystem at the same time it can accurately locate any device in the ecosystem. In this every device is given with an authentication number which is used to login into the framework ones logged in the devices become unison with the framework.

Coming to data control and management centre it acts as the brain to entire framework in which all data are stored, all analytics are done, all the decision and response are decided and it's a place which monitor the framework as whole. It's also responsible for the security and reliability of the system. This data control and management centre is same like cloud database centre but it uses the physical framework to connect between devices when optimised the dependency on the internet is greatly reduced. The total framework works like grid computing.

4.3.1 PATH SELECTION

Managing and organizing the movement of the vehicle is established as path planning technique. Path planning technique is modelled using artificial intelligence and deep learning architecture in the control unit on processing the information such as the signals, signs and speed limits integrated within them. As are devices are interconnected any real time change in the environment can be added to the system to avoid disasters. Virtual Path generates the control signal using AI technique as to control the movement of the vehicle. Control signal contain the routing map with route information to the autonomous vehicle. The data sent to the device takes the shortest route in the tow option.

Every optical fibre line is designated with a route number and every transceiver in an optical fibre line is given with a specific identify associated with the route number. Using this information, the virtual pathway is built upon this Routing Algorithm. This acts as a map for automated vehicles.

Vehicle is arranged as per control signal propagating in the network with respect to vehicle movement and quality of the vehicle link computation periodically at regular intervals [13]. Each Vehicle Nodes represented in a distributed manner on basis of its changing direction. Further path plan for data communication containing the traffic information of the environment is propagated through transceiver.

4.3.3 ALGORITHM 1: VIRTUAL PATH PLANNING

Projection of the Network

AV is No. of Autonomous Vehicle in the Environment

T is No of Transceiver in the Environment employed for path planning

Control Signal $C_d = \text{Routing Map}(\{S_p, D, R_d\})$

Virtual path ()

for $C_d = AV_1$ to AV_n

{

Compute Shortest Distance ()

Determine the Road Traffic () $T = \{ \text{no of vehicle in specified Distance} \}$

If ($T < \text{Threshold}$)

Fix vehicle in the route map for transportation

Else

Compute next alternate path

Fig 4.2 working module diagram

4.4 BLOCK DAIGRAM

In the block one could see all the optical fibre connecting the Transceivers start from the data management and control. And every transceiver is connected with one another by an optical fibre and wirelessly, A virtual pathway is created above the optical fibres and Transceiver which is used for the navigation of automated vehicles in smart cities. Every device in the ecosystem can be seen to connected to tow transceiver at a time and also connected to every other device in the ecosystem which can facilitate better integrated working of smart devices in the ecosystem.

All Optical fibre lines are given with a route number and every transceiver is given with an identification number. Every device that's connected to the framework become a part and unison with the framework itself. By which one could remotely control any device in smart cities by using the data control and management centre after being authorised to proceed the specific task.

4.5 ADVANTAGES

- With the proposed system every device in a smart city can be connected without any loss of signal and signal strength. Every device is connected with the same high-speed data transfer network.
- The proposed system can accommodate and facilitate the development of smart and automated devices, like IoT devices and sensors, automated vehicles and drones, smart gadgets and applications.
- The automated vehicles will be able to navigate in and around a pathway which works real time, getting inputs from the environment from the external sensors by which the decision making of automated vehicle is elevated to level that's better than the decision making of a human.
- Automated Drones and other Ariel vehicles can now navigate without any human intervention or overseeing as the virtual pathway is projected upon a physical road and every detail and real time changes are updated to the automated Drones by the framework it in turn help the drones from crashing into buildings and having a mid-air collation.
- The framework using the software analytics of the data control and management centre can feed real time traffic in the area to the automated vehicle and also the other vehicles movement and information is shared for better real time understanding of the route the vehicle is taking.

4.6 ADVANTAGES OVER CLOUD

- Adopting cloud solutions on a small scale and for short-term projects can be perceived as being as a whole cloud computing is considered to be very expensive to operate. Whereas in the proposed system small scale and short-term projects could be developed using the framework and which is way cheaper than cloud computing.
- Vendor lock-in is another perceived disadvantage of cloud computing. Easy switching between cloud services is a service that hasn't yet completely evolved, and

organizations may find it difficult to migrate their services from one vendor to another. With the proposed system we bring in Web 3.0 approach to data control and management which enables the easy switching between the vendors.

- Downtime is often cited as one of the biggest disadvantages of cloud computing. Since cloud computing systems are internet-based, service outages are always an unfortunate possibility and can occur for any reason whereas in the proposed system the downtime is reduced significantly that it becomes unnoticeable by the user and the systems.

HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In this we will see about the physical hardware required to make the proposed system functional these units as the devices are instrumental in creating spheres of internet.

5.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The hardware Requirements for the system are as follows:

- Transceiver
- Optical fiber
- Amplifier
- Solar panel
- Battery

5.3 POWER SUPPLY

The system is decided in way that it can relay on the existing systems like the power grid for its primary power source. At the same time the battery can be used for the user end devices. Overall, the power supply is designed in a way that it consumes the power from existing infrastructure.

5.4 TRANSCEIVER

Transceiver is a device that can simultaneously receive and send data we use a full duplex transceiver. A transceiver is a combination transmitter/receiver in a single package. While the term typically applies to wireless communications devices, it can also be used for transmitter/receiver devices in cable or optical fiber systems. It can both transmit signals over the network wire and detect electrical signals flowing through the wire. The specification of the transceiver

- Full-duplex transceivers. The radio transmitter and receiver can work in parallel. Transmission and reception take place on different radio frequencies. This mode is observed in handheld and mobile two-way radios.

In a transceiver the transmitter and receiver operate on different frequencies to avoid the interference of the signal and damage caused by a transmitter on the receiver.

FIG 5.1 BLOCK DIAGRAM OF A TRANSCEIVER

5.5 OPTICAL FIBER

Optical fiber refers to the technology that transmits information as light pulses along a glass or plastic fiber. A fiberoptic cable can contain a varying number of these glass fibers – from a few up to a couple hundred. Another glass layer, called cladding, surrounds the glass fiber core. The buffer tube layer protects the cladding, and a jacket layer acts as the final protective layer for the individual strand. Fiber optic cables are commonly used because of their advantages over copper cables. Some of those benefits include higher bandwidth and transmit speeds. Fiber optics is used for long-distance and high-performance data networking. It is also commonly used in telecommunication services

In wavelength-division multiplexed channels in a 4-core optical fiber a speed of 319 Tb/s Achieved in a long-haul transmission of wideband (>120 nm) S, C and L-bands signal using 552 PDM-16QAM for distance of 3000km. With this level of internet speed is required to Integrate in advanced smart cities by implementing this system the human race can accelerate the development to become a higher Intelligent civilization.

5.6 AMPLIFIER

Amplifier is the generic term used to describe a circuit which produces an increased version of its input signal and output signal. Amplifiers are used in the system to amplify the relayed signal which may be subjected to a loss of strength due to the wireless transmission. We deploy an amplifier with a higher gain ratio.

Fig 5.2 representation of an amplifier in a circuit

5.7 SOLAR PANEL

Solar panels use sunlight as a source of energy to generate direct current electricity. A collection of PV modules is called a PV panel, and a system of PV panels is called an array. Arrays of a photovoltaic system supply solar electricity to electrical equipment. The Solar panel in the system is used as backup power source to power the system in case of power cuts or natural disasters. A solar panel is placed for every transceiver

5.8 BATTERY

Battery is setup in the proposed system as a Power backup which is charged both the main supply and Solar panel the Solar panel is used at the times of disaster and power cuts. When the time of main current source fails it the battery that gives power backup to the transceiver and the framework.

SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we see about the software's used in this project. Software is a set of instructions, data or programs used to operate computers and execute specific tasks. It is the opposite of hardware, which describes the physical aspects of a computer. Software is a generic

term used to refer to applications, scripts and programs that run on a device. It can be thought of as the variable part of a computer, while hardware is the invariable part.

6.2 DATA CENTER MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE

Although adoption is on the rise, some confusion still exists in much of the user community over what DCIM is and what it should do. IN general, however, DCIM is a software suite for managing data center infrastructure and the resources it uses. DCIM tools collect data from IT and facilities, constate it into relevant information and report it in real time to enable the intelligent management, optimization and future planning of data center resources such as capacity, power, cooling, space, network and assets.

Vendors can incorporate all, most or just some of the following categories that fall under this definition:

- Energy and environmental monitoring
- Asset and workflow management
- Data center visualization
- Capacity planning and what-if scenarios
- Structured cable management
- Network management and optimization
- Centralized and remote monitoring
- Event reporting and management

AI and machine learning (ML) optimization

6.3 SUNBIRD DCIM:

Sunbird's DCIM is one of the few solutions on the market that focuses exclusively on two of the biggest and costliest challenges data center operators face: monitoring and operations. And unlike other DCIM providers, who offer overly complex, bloated and expensive software, Sunbird's solution is easy to deploy and use. It provides the ability to better manage assets, change and capacity; and also enables power monitoring, environmental monitoring and energy management.

Sunbird DCIM Data Centre Management Features: Audit Trail, Device Auto Discovery, Diagnostic Testing, Import/Export Data, Multi-Platform, Multi-User Collaboration, Power Management

6.4 ECO STRUXURE

EcoStruxure IT Software is Schneider Electric's DCIM – Data Center Infrastructure Management – solution for advanced monitoring, planning, and modelling of local edge sites, data center, and colocation infrastructures. EcoStruxure IT Software provides wherever-you-go visibility into the health of the IT supporting digital transformations – such as UPS, rack PDU, cooling equipment, etc. Asset tracking, and data-driven recommendations. The software helps mitigate security and failure risks, reduce operational cost, and optimize operations with automate workflow, preventive management, and risk management

EcoStruxure Data Center Management Features: Audit Trail, Behaviour-Based Acceleration, Cross Reference System, Device Auto Discovery, Diagnostic Testing, Import/Export Data, JCL Management, Multi-Platform, Multi-User, Power Management, Sarbanes-Oxley Compliance

6.5 RIT -XPEDITE

The way that Tesla has transformed the world with autonomous cars, this is our vision for RiT – XpedITe – “to make data centres autonomous”. This is achieved by bringing intelligence to the physical data centre through one federated management software platform. RiT – XpedITe is the only data centre infrastructure management system (DCIM) on the market which gives our clients a solution that connects infrastructure and network in one platform, while fully automating and optimising its daily operation

RiT – XpedITe Data Center Management Features: Audit Trail, Import/Export Data, Multi-Platform, Multi-User Collaboration, Power Management

Fig 6.1 representation of layers in rit Xpedite

6.7 ORACLE DATABASE

An Oracle database is a collection of data treated as a unit. The purpose of a database is to store and retrieve related information. A database server is the key to solving the problems of information management. In general, a server reliably manages a large amount of data in a multiuser environment so that many users can concurrently access the same data. All this is accomplished while delivering high performance. A database server also prevents unauthorized access and provides efficient solutions for failure recovery.

Oracle Database is the first database designed for enterprise grid computing, the most flexible and cost-effective way to manage information and applications. Enterprise grid computing creates large pools of industry-standard, modular storage and servers. With this architecture, each new system can be rapidly provisioned from the pool of components. There is no need for peak workloads, because capacity can be easily added or reallocated from the resource pools as needed.

The database has logical structures and physical structures. Because the physical and logical structures are separate, the physical storage of data can be managed without affecting the access to logical storage structures

Fig 6.2 architecture of oracle databases

6.8 GRID COMPUTING

The grid style of computing treats collections of similar IT resources holistically as a single pool, while exploiting the distinct nature of individual resources within the pool. To address simultaneously the problems of monolithic systems and fragmented resources, grid computing achieves a balance between the benefits of holistic resource management and flexible independent resource control. IT resources managed in a grid include:

- Infrastructure: the hardware and software that create a data storage and program execution environment
- Applications: the program logic and flow that define specific business processes
- Information: the meanings inherent in all different types of data used to conduct business

Fig 6.3 working of grid computing

6.8.1 BENEFIT OF GRID COMPUTING

- Compared to other models of computing, IT systems designed and implemented in the grid style deliver higher quality of service, lower cost, and greater flexibility.
- Higher quality of service results from having no single point of failure, a robust security infrastructure, and centralized, policy-driven management.
- Lower costs derive from increasing the utilization of resources and dramatically reducing management and maintenance costs. Rather than dedicating a stack of software and hardware to a specific task, all resources are pooled and allocated on demand, thus eliminating underutilized capacity and redundant capabilities.
- Grid computing also enables the use of smaller individual hardware components, thus reducing the cost of each individual component and providing more flexibility to devote resources in accordance with changing needs

6.9 GRID COMPUTING IN ORACLE DATABASE

On the path toward this grand vision of grid computing, companies need real solutions to support their incremental moves toward a more flexible and more productive IT architecture. The Oracle Database 10g family of software products implements much of the core grid technology to get companies started. And Oracle delivers this grid computing functionality in the context of holistic enterprise architecture, providing a robust security infrastructure,

centralized management, intuitive, powerful development tools, and universal access. Oracle Database 10g includes:

- Oracle Database 10g
- Oracle Application Server 10g
- Oracle Enterprise Manager 10g
- Oracle Collaboration Suite 10g

Although the grid features of Oracle 10g span all of the products listed above, this discussion will focus on the grid computing capabilities of Oracle Database 10g

6.10 IBM WATSON ANALYTICS

IBM Watson is an AI-augmented data science solution that enables employees to harness the power of proprietary data, unlock its potential and apply insights gained from it in new ways. It offers a wide variety of customizable modules for lifecycle management, data applications, APIs and industry-focused specializations.

6.10.1 Advantages of IBM Watson

- **Enrich Data Interactions:** Reduced reaction times give users nearly instantaneous access to data. The solution can be trained to prioritize common requests in order to optimize future interactions with users.
- **Apply and Discover Data:** Speedy data discovery helps process millions of data points in a timely manner to get on with the work that matters most.
- **Anticipate and Prevent Disruptions:** Identify potential issues in workflows that can cause long-lasting damage to an organization using AI and pattern identification.
- **Detect and Mitigate Risks:** Security measures like role-based access, single sign-on and advanced learning combine to create a secure system that protects data from theft and leakage. Train the solution to adapt to and follow the latest privacy regulations to preemptively discover compliance breaches.
- **Democratize Access and Use:** Foster data literacy throughout the organization by utilizing employee knowledge combined with industry teachings and empower the whole workforce through AI-augmented learning.
- **Customize and Teach the System:** It learns as it is used to adapt to individual user's needs and habits through AI, NLP and machine learning.
- **Gain a Competitive Advantage:** Using the data already available to an organization, managers can predict the shape of future trends that will affect their business. It also positions businesses to remain agile in the face of changes.

7.1 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this part, proposed architecture has been simulated in NS2 Simulator with generation of virtual path for autonomous vehicle movement in the various paths [15]. Extensive simulation of the model exploits the performances results of the model in handling the dynamic traffic to the transceiver against the conventional models. The performance outcome of the proposed model has been represented with respect to the placement of the vehicle in the environment and its surrounding to measure the network overhead and latency. Simulation set up of the proposed framework is defined in the table 1

Table 1: Simulation of Autonomous vehicle Path Planning Parameters

Simulation features	Value
Model Simulating Software	NS2
Environment size	500m *500m
No. Of Autonomous vehicles	20
Channel bandwidth	50Mbps
Control signal file size	50 bytes
Simulation Time	40 minutes

The autonomous vehicle is operated automatically with the control signal generated from the control unit is illustrated in the figure 7.1. Control signal carries the route map with speed of vehicle, source and destination, sign signals, road clusters and road traffic etc.

Figure 7.1: Proposed Protocol Simulation

Each autonomous vehicle is evaluated with capability of the transceiver in managing the number of the signal on its environment with dynamic traffic condition. The performance of the framework is computed on changing the network size and moving node speed has been computed on basis of the latency and overhead in the figure 7.2 to the changing direction of the nodes.

Figure 7.2: Performance evaluation with respect to (a) Overhead and (b) Latency

The proposed virtual path planning techniques has been evaluated on the reliability and sustainability of the network on the virtual path generated for transportation of vehicle with shortest hop count..

Table 2 – Performance Evaluation against various data traffic in the network

Technique	Network Overhead in mbps	Routing Latency
Existing	15.23	0.35
Proposed	12.59	0.26

The changing in the network size in real time affects the performance of autonomous vehicles significantly as the density of the network and the total traffic loads increases leads to high transmission delay.

CONCLUSION

Distributed failure tolerant path planning framework has been designed and implemented to generate the virtual path for automated vehicles like drone and grounded vehicles. Proposed model integrates architecture with the Amazon or IBM webserver to gather and manage the network data and its communications using artificial intelligence. Virtual path planning algorithm is developed to control the autonomous vehicles on extracting the various information from the sensor component in the ecosystem using telecommunication network. Base station also categories and schedules the data efficiently to reduce the computation time and cost. Controlled signal containing the route map is transferred to transceiver built-in in the autonomous devices through trajectory of the intermediate transceivers. Control signal carries the information of the virtual path plan as route map containing the route number of the optical fiber channel and specific identification number of transceiver representing start and end point destinations for movement. Finally transceiver communicates the information like speed limit, signal indication like one ways and closed roads etc.

FUTURE WORK

- The same framework can be used to provide high speed internet
- The framework is will be able to accommodate advanced robots and humanoids
- Living creatures can be accommodated and facilities by placing bio tags on them.
- Commenting entire world into one single framework.

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Citation: Mukesh, V., Joel, D., Balaji, V. M., Tamilpriyan, R., & Yogesh Pandian, S. (2024). Data management and creation of routes for automated vehicles in smart city. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(36), 2119–2150.

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